

Base Camp Quality of Life Standardization and Improvement

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Abstract—The United States (US) Army has over 66,000 soldiers engaged in contingency operations across the world. Current budgetary constraints and an uncertain global security environment require these operations to be executed as efficiently as possible. Base camps are the secured areas where soldiers live when deployed to contingency operations. Base camps impose a significant financial and tactical burden during contingency operations and sub-optimal soldier quality of life decisions have significantly contributed to costs. Quality of life (QOL) refers to the non-security and non-mission related services that directly sustain the mission effectiveness of soldiers. Current US Army base camp tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs) do not sufficiently specify QOL services, and more detailed doctrine should be developed to support combat units executing contingency operations. In this investigation we employ quantitative methods to select decisions that improve QOL and inform doctrine. We leverage a QOL function and resource consumption data developed by US Army Natick Soldier Research, Development and Engineering Center’s (Natick Labs) to build a model that improves QOL under the constraints of four fundamental resources: fuel, water, waste water, and solid waste. We employ a mixed integer linear program modeling approach and execute sensitivity analysis to evaluate the strength of our results. Our final model is formulated as a chance constraint optimization to address the uncertainty associated with resource availability in contingency operations. Our results provide QOL decisions that reduce resource consumption while maintaining an equivalent QOL level when compared to current TTPs. The model provides quantitative rigor, informing decision makers of specific base camp design principles for the development of doctrine.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Problem Description and Definition

The United States of America’s (US) strategic policy requires that the US Army execute sustained contingency operations across the world. The objectives of these contingency operations span the range from high-intensity lethal engagements to disaster and humanitarian relief; however, all these require a globally distributed troop presence. [27] This presence is enabled by base camps - areas where soldiers live while conducting contingency operations, and where their mission effectiveness is maintained or improved. [6] Coupled with operational requirements are the contemporary budgetary constraints placed upon the US Army - while demand for the Army grows, available resources are being reduced. To

maintain a force that can project power with agility, the US Army must establish efficient base camp design doctrine. [3]

We provide a methodology to maintain soldier mission effectiveness under resource constraints by recommending base camp design doctrine that improves quality of life (QOL) while using less resources. QOL on US Army base camps depends upon the essential services provided to soldiers to maintain their mission effectiveness in contingency operations. [5] The principal resources that constrain QOL on base camps are fuel, water, waste water, and solid waste. [20] These four constraining resources represent a fundamental subset of the resources that limit the US Army’s ability to project power in distributed global contingency operations.

Currently subject matter experts employ anecdotal experiences to inform Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (TTPs) that are used for base camp design standards. These TTPs are provided in regional command Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) documents; however, the US Army has not established base camp design doctrine implementing standard QOL services across all organizations. [12], [13] The lack of doctrine for base camp design, and resulting QOL, results in inefficient resource consumption and high costs measured in monetary expense and reduced operational capabilities. [3], [18]

The methodology we provide optimizes QOL on US Army base camps, accounting for interactions among dozens of QOL services, constraining resources, and uncertainty. Current practice employing anecdotal subject matter expert decision making alone to dictate TTPs does not rigorously account for the complex interactions and trade-offs present when designing and operating a base camp in contingency operations.

B. Modeling Approach and Limitations

We start to address this problem by leveraging research from US Army Natick Soldier Research, Development and Engineering Center’s (Natick Labs) Sustainable and Logistics Basing Science and Technology Objective Demonstration (SLB-STO-D). Natick Labs SLB-STO-D has built a QOL function that measures soldier QOL on US Army base camps based upon *QOL decisions* made when designing the camps. [2], [5] These QOL decisions include hygiene services, food quality, heating and cooling of living space, and Morale Welfare Recreation (MWR) options - all fundamental services that maintain soldier mission effectiveness in contingency

operations. Employing additional research that was executed at Natick Labs SLB-STO-D we measure each QOL decision’s contribution to the consumption of fuel, water, and subsequent production of waste water, and solid waste. Using all this information we formulate a deterministic Base Camps Mixed Integer Program (BCMIP). We reformulate the BCMIP to include chance constraints (BCMIP-CC) in order to account for the uncertainty associated with resource availability, which we optimize for recommended QOL decisions to inform base camp design doctrine. [20], [25]

C. Summary of Contributions

Our investigation provides three contributions. First we formulate a specific methodology for improving base camp QOL using the BCMIP. To validate the performance of the BCMIP we compare our recommended QOL decisions to current US Army QOL TTPs. Next we investigate how QOL is affected by changes in the BCMIP parameters including resource availability, the marginal usage of resources with each QOL decision, and the contribution of each QOL decision towards soldier mission effectiveness. Finally, we provide a methodology for the optimization of base camp QOL under uncertain resource constraints by developing the BCMIP-CC. The BCMIP-CC provides decision makers with parameters that can be used to optimize base camp design given terrain restrictions and the mission. By refining and employing the BCMIP-CC methodology we believe US Army decision makers have the tools to develop base camp design doctrine.

II. TECHNICAL APPROACH

US Army decision makers design individual base camps, and hence influence QOL based on personal experience and current TTPs. [2], [18] We build upon this approach by developing the BCMIP, which determines optimized QOL decisions that improve soldier mission effectiveness under constraints on resource availability. This methodology leverages both the qualitative knowledge of a population of base camp subject matter experts and mathematical optimization. We accomplish this by first using a QOL function developed by Federici et al. at Natick Labs. [5] Next, we calculate the marginal utilization of each QOL decision for each limited resource, establish historical resource availability levels, and formulate the BCMIP to determine optimized QOL decisions for base camps. Finally, we formulate chance constraints in the BCMIP-CC to find the best QOL decisions given uncertainty associated with contingency operations.

A. Related Work

Literature from both civilian and military investigations informed our understanding of soldier QOL and the resource constraints encountered on US Army base camps in contingency operations. Medical journal articles were critical to our evaluation of the QOL model developed at Natick Labs SLB-STO-D, including work by Spitzer et al. and Ramsey et al. [5], [22] Military QOL studies were informative given our application of a qualitative function to a military population.

[26], [33] Our formulation of the resource constraints on base camps was informed by investigations from Anderson and motivated by the work of Marsh and the Noblis Corporation. [1], [3], [16], [18], [20]

The parameters of the BCMIP were developed based on technical reports completed by Natick Labs SLB-STO-D. Our QOL objective function was developed from referencing the work of Federici et al. who surveyed a population of US Army base camp subject matter experts and employed conjoint analysis to establish relative “part-worth” values for each QOL decision. [5] Our methodology was also informed by previous work concerning the impact of resource constraints on QOL by Augustyn et al. [2]

The formulation of the BCMIP-CC provides the capability to optimize QOL while accounting for resource uncertainty. To develop this formulation we employed a chance constraint optimization model influenced by the work of Ruszczyński. [25]

B. Base Camp Mixed Integer Program (BCMIP)

Our initial methodology employed a mixed integer program to provide optimized QOL decisions on US Army base camps under the deterministic constraints of fuel, water, waste water, and solid waste. We refer to this initial formulation as the Base Camp Mixed Integer Program (BCMIP). Current US Army base camp design produces a lower QOL score when compared to the decisions recommended by the BCMIP. The QOL score is produced by an objective function and used to compare the QOL provided to soldiers given varying QOL decisions. [5] With a fixed amount of resources, our optimized QOL decisions achieve a score of 16.5 compared with the current baseline score of 13.7 - a 20% increase in QOL with no additional resource consumption. The baseline QOL decisions that are currently employed on base camps and those decisions recommended by the BCMIP are provided in Table I.

QOL Decision	Current Standards with 100% resources	Optimized Decisions with 100% resources
Shower	Hot 10 minute	Hot 5 minute
Laundry Bags	2 per week	1 per week
Latrines	Flush	Flush
Breakfast	MRE	UGR-A
Lunch	MRE	MRE
Dinner	UGR-A	UGR-A
Refrigerated Beverages	Not Available	Available
Ice Available	Not Available	Not Available
Enhanced Food	Not Available	Available
Gym	Cardio	Cardio and Weight
MWR	Basic	Improved
Mail Facility	Available	Available
HVAC	High	High
QOL Score	13.7439	16.572

TABLE I: Quality of Life Decision Comparison[6], [9], [12], [13]

To evaluate the sensitivity of the BCMIP results given uncertainty in the model parameters, we performed numerical

sensitivity analysis. In this sensitivity analysis we perturbed all the parameter values of the BCMIP individually, iteratively re-optimizing the BCMIP with each perturbation. We compared the results of each re-optimization to previous iterations. We determined that QOL on US Army base camps is most sensitive to the fuel and water constraints. The details of the BCMIP formulation and sensitivity analysis are available in Kuiper. [17]

This result aligned with practical research in the design and sustainment of US Army base camps in contingency operations where the supply of fuel and water acutely impacted the QOL. [20] With these results we developed a new formulation using chance constraints (BCMIP-CC) in order to account for the uncertainty associated with fuel and water supply.

In the next section we describe the formulation of BCMIP-CC, which includes chance constraints on resource availability.

C. BCMIP-CC Formulation

1) *Sets*: The set of QOL decisions established by decision makers designing base camps is denoted by S . These QOL decisions are the services on base camps that have the most impact on soldier mission effectiveness in contingency operations and are listed in Table II. [17]

Members of Set S: Quality of Life Decisions		
i	S_i	Description
1	Cold 5 minute Shower	10° temp change for 5 minutes
2	Warm 5 min Shower	20° temp change for 5 min
3	Hot 5 min Shower	30° temp change for 5 min
4	Cold 10 min Shower	10° temp change for 10 min
5	Warm 10 min Shower	20° temp change for 10 min
6	Hot 10 min Shower	30° temp change for 10 min
7	Cold 15 min Shower	10° temp change for 15 min
8	Warm 15 min Shower	20° temp change for 15 min
9	Hot 15 min Shower	30° temp change for 15 min
10	Number of Laundry Bags	Number of Laundry Bags Daily
11	Burn Out Toilets	Burn Disposal Latrines
12	Chemical Toilets	Chemically Treated Latrines
13	Flush Toilets	Latrines with Full Plumbing
14	Breakfast MRE	Warm Meal for Breakfast
15	Breakfast UGR-E	Improved Combat Ration for Breakfast
16	Breakfast UGR-A	Basic Combat Ration for Breakfast
17	Lunch MRE	Warm Meal for Lunch
18	Lunch UGR-E	Improved Combat Ration for Lunch
19	Lunch UGR-A	Basic Combat Ration for Lunch
20	Dinner MRE	Warm Meal for Dinner
21	Dinner UGR-E	Improved Combat Ration for Dinner
22	Dinner UGR-A	Basic Combat Ration for Dinner
23	Refrigerated Beverage	Refrigerated Beverages Available
24	Ice Available	Bagged Ice Available at all Times
25	Enhanced Food	Additional Food Available between Meals
26	Cardio Gym	Fitness Center with Cardiovascular Equipment
27	Weight Gym	Fitness Center with Weight Equipment
28	Basic MWR	Small MWR with 2 TVs
29	Improved MWR	Large MWR with 6 TVs
30	Mail Facility	Distribute and Hold Mail
31	Medium HVAC	Medium Level of HVAC
32	High HVAC	High Level of HVAC
33	Laundry Indicator	Indicator Variable for Laundry
34	Hot Meal Indicator	Indicator Variable for Hot Meals

TABLE II: $S \equiv$ set of camp quality of life decisions

QOL and resulting soldier mission effectiveness on base camps is constrained by a set of fundamental resources that impose an enormous burden on contingency operations in mission capabilities and financial costs. This set of constraining resources, R , is provided in Table III.

Members of Set R: Limited Resources			
j	R_j	Resources	Unit
1	Fuel	Diesel Fuel	$\frac{\text{gallons}}{\text{soldier daily}}$
2	Water	Water	$\frac{\text{gallons}}{\text{soldier daily}}$
3	Waste Water	Waste Water	$\frac{\text{gallons}}{\text{soldier daily}}$
4	Solid Waste	Solid Waste	$\frac{\text{pounds}}{\text{soldier daily}}$

TABLE III: $R \equiv$ set of limited resources available on a base camp

To account for the uncertainty associated with resource supply, many decision makers naively under-estimate the amount of resources available when designing base camps. For example a decision maker may design a base camp assuming 2 gallons of fuel available per day per soldier, while actually expecting to receive 3 gallons of fuel per day per soldier. Naively planning for a lower amount of water or fuel when designing base camp QOL decisions is designed to account for the possibility of missed resupply or inefficient service. While this method may provide an adequate surplus of resource supply, it does not give decision makers the tools to make optimized base camp design decisions based upon operational requirements. A more rigorous methodology that mitigates uncertainty is to employ a relative frequency distribution of resource availability, and to optimize QOL under the assumption of this distribution with some level of certainty. [23].

We establish the set Ω of resource availability scenarios for the base camp and vary the availability of water and fuel according to the probabilistic event of missed resource deliveries. For example, referencing Table IV for Scenario 10 we see a joint event has occurred where 2 days' fuel and 1 day's water delivery have been missed. As a result, there will be a 75% decrease in available fuel and 50% decrease water on the base camp.

Members of Set Ω				
Missed deliveries by resource	No days missed fuel	1 day missed fuel	2 days missed fuel	3 days missed fuel
No days missed water	Scenario 1	Scenario 5	Scenario 9	Scenario 13
1 day missed water	Scenario 2	Scenario 6	Scenario 10	Scenario 14
2 days missed water	Scenario 3	Scenario 7	Scenario 11	Scenario 15
3 days missed water	Scenario 4	Scenario 8	Scenario 12	Scenario 16

TABLE IV: $\Omega \equiv$ set of scenarios describing the availability of resources

Each set member $\omega \in \Omega$ represents a scenario that specifically describes the resources available to the base camp, which is determined by the joint probabilistic event of whether a planned fuel and / or water delivery does or does not occur daily. We reduced the availability of fuel and / or water by -50% in the event that a delivery to the base camp is missed.

2) *Parameters*: Parameters provide the numerical specification for the BCMIP-CC. These values are indexed by the three sets we previously established: QOL decisions \mathbf{S} , resources \mathbf{R} , and resource availability scenarios Ω . We introduce six parameters for the BCMIP-CC: QOL objective function coefficients, resource availability values, marginal use values, a discrete probability distribution for resource availability, resupply uncertainty value, and risk. We provide a description of these parameters; exact values may be referenced in Base Camp Standardization and Improvement by Kuiper. [17]

The QOL objective function coefficients, $q_i \in \mathbb{R}_+$, where $i \in \mathbf{S}$, describe how much each QOL decision contributes towards a soldier's QOL. These values were developed by surveying a population of base camp subject matter experts and employing conjoint analysis to develop part-worths of each QOL decision. [19] These coefficients values were taken from an analysis executed by Natick Labs SLB-STO-D. [5]

The parameter $b_{j,\omega}$ describes the availability of each resource, $j \in \mathbf{R}$, given a specific resource availability scenario, $\omega \in \Omega$, where $b_{j,\omega} \in \mathbb{R}_+$. In Equation 1 we provide the relationship used to calculate resource availability.

Resource Availability Calculation :

$$b_{j,\omega} = (b_{j, \text{Scenario } 1}) \times (l^{m_{j,\omega}}), \text{ where:}$$

$$l = \text{loss factor constant of } .5$$

$$m_{j,\omega} = \text{number of missed resupply for resource } j$$

$$\text{and scenario } \omega; \text{ where } m_{j,\omega} \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}^\dagger$$

† Reference *Table IV* for scenario specification of $m_{j,\omega}$ (1)

The marginal use parameter quantifies how much each QOL decision costs in terms of each resource. For example if decision makers design base camps with the QOL decision of 10 minute cold showers, then a specific amount of fuel is consumed to pump and heat water, water is consumed to provide the shower, and waste water is produced as a result of the shower. The marginal use values for each QOL decision were calculated referencing consumption models developed by Natick Labs SLB-STO-D. We represent these values with $u_{i,j} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ where $i, j \in \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{R}$.

The parameter $p_{j,\omega} \in [0, 1]$, $j, \omega \in \mathbf{R}, \Omega$ specifies the discrete probability distribution of resource availability. These probabilities quantify the likelihood of each resource availability scenario. Our scenarios, indexed by set Ω , only describe the possibility of reduced fuel and water levels. We employed a joint truncated geometric distribution, where $m_{fuel,\omega} = \mathcal{X} \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ is the random variable of the number of water deliveries missed and the random variable $m_{water,\omega} = \mathcal{Y} \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ is the number of fuel deliveries missed.

Resource Availability Distribution :

$$p_{j,\omega} = \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{X} = x, \mathcal{Y} = y) = \left(\frac{d(1-d)^{x-1}}{1-(1-d)^n}\right) \left(\frac{d(1-d)^{y-1}}{1-(1-d)^n}\right),$$

$$j, \omega \in \mathbf{R}, \Omega; \text{ and } n = 4 \text{ days} \quad (2)$$

The final parameters of the BCMIP-CC, are the resource resupply uncertainty value $d \in [0, 1]$, used in Equation 2, and the likelihood of infeasibility of the results or risk associated with the model, represented by $\epsilon_j \in [0, 1]$, where $j \in \mathbf{R}$. For the model we evaluated we assumed a constant $\epsilon_j = \epsilon \forall j \in \mathbf{R}$.

3) *Decision Variables and Objective Function*: The decision variable x_i is the QOL decision, $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$, $i \in \mathbf{S}$, where $x_i = 1$ if decision i is selected and $x_i = 0$ otherwise. The decision variable x_{10} is the exception to this definition, where $x_{10} \in \mathbb{Z}$, or the set of integers.

Our decision variable $z_{j,\omega}$ is the indicator variable for the robustness of the BCMIP-CC to the availability of resource $j \in \mathbf{R}$ for scenario $\omega \in \Omega$, where $z_{j,\omega} \in \{0, 1\}$. $z_{j,\omega} = 0$ if the BCMIP-CC is robust to scenario ω , or $z_{j,\omega} = 1$ if the BCMIP-CC is not robust to scenario ω .

The BCMIP-CC assumes a linear relationship between decision variables. With this relationship, and referencing Natick Labs SLB-STO-D research, our model uses a linear objective function employing the QOL coefficients q_i , to be multiplied by each QOL decision: $x_1 q_1 + x_2 q_2 + \dots + x_n q_n$. [5] We refer to the value generated by this function as the *QOL score*. This is the function we optimize in order to determine improved QOL decisions.

Total Quality of Life (QOL Score)

$$\sum_{i \in \mathbf{S}} q_i x_i \quad (3)$$

In order to determine the optimized or *Recommended QOL Decisions* for doctrinal base camp design we find the Argument Maximum ($\arg \max$) of the objective function, Equation 3, of the BCMIP-CC.

4) *Constraints*: Analyzing the relationship between each QOL decision and limited resources is critical to improving soldiers' mission effectiveness while executing contingency operations. We define linear constraint relationships, quantifying the amount that each quality of life decision variable, x_i , consumes of each resource availability scenario, $b_{j,\omega}$, measured per person daily.

The marginal use values for each resource, $u_{i,j}$, provides the multiplicative link between QOL decisions and resource availability. The resource availability chance constraint relationships ensure that the QOL decisions recommended by the BCMIP-CC do not consume more resources than available on the camp. The amount of resources available is provided by the discrete distribution of resource availability scenarios. A generalized constraint inequality considering all resource availability scenarios, $b_{j,\omega}$ and all potential QOL decisions, x_i is provided in Equation 4.

Resource Chance Constraints :

$$\sum_{i \in \mathbf{S}} u_{i,j} x_i + z_{j,\omega} b_{j,\omega} \leq b_{j,\omega} \forall j, \omega \in \mathbf{R}, \Omega \quad (4)$$

With the BCMIP-CC formulation the resource availability levels are not fixed; instead a distribution of scenarios that provide varying levels of resources are used to constrain the BCMIP-CC. The probability constraint, shown in Equation 5 provides additional resources to the BCMIP-CC, loosening the constraints associated with Equation 4 as the BCMIP-CC model optimizes over the binary decision variable $z_{j,\omega}$. The additional resources provided to the model are controlled by the risk parameter ϵ . With the relationship between Equations 4 and 5 we see that ϵ controls what resource availability scenarios the BCMIP-CC does not account for.

Probability Constraint :

$$\sum_{\omega \in \Omega} p_{j,\omega} z_{j,\omega} \leq \epsilon_j \forall j \in \mathbf{R} \quad (5)$$

In addition to these two primary constraints, there are a number of logical constraints that are formulated to enforce the physical structure of base camps. These constraints include: fixed cost constraints associated with generator implementation, policy restrictions on base camps, and decision variable restrictions. The full formulation of the BCMIP-CC is described in detail by Kuiper and provided in Table V. [17]

MAXIMIZE:	
Description	Equation
Total QOL Score	$\sum_{i \in \mathbf{S}} q_i x_i$
SUBJECT TO:	
Resource Chance Constraint	$\sum_{i \in \mathbf{S}} u_{i,j} x_i + z_{j,\omega} b_{j,\omega} \leq b_{j,\omega} \forall j, \omega \in \mathbf{R}, \Omega$
Probability Constraint	$\sum_{\omega \in \Omega} p_{j,\omega} z_{j,\omega} \leq \epsilon_j \forall j \in \mathbf{R}$
Shower Constraint	$x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 + x_7 + x_8 + x_9 \leq 1$
Breakfast Choice	$x_{14} + x_{15} + x_{16} = 1$
Lunch Choice	$x_{17} + x_{18} + x_{19} = 1$
Diner Choice	$x_{20} + x_{21} + x_{22} = 1$
Latrine Choice	$x_{11} + x_{12} + x_{13} = 1$
MWR Choice	$x_{27} + x_{28} = 1$
HVAC Choice	$x_{31} + x_{32} = 1$
Laundry Fixed	$7x_{33} \geq x_{10}$
Laundry Bag Limit	$x_{10} \leq 7$
Meal Fixed Cost	$x_{16} + x_{19} + x_{22} \geq x_{34}$
Meal Fixed Cost	$x_{16} + x_{19} + x_{22} \leq 3x_{34}$
Binary Decision Variables	$x_{1-9} \in \{0, 1\}$
Integer Decision Variables	$x_{10} \in \mathbb{Z}^1$
Binary Decision Variables	$x_{11-34} \in \{0, 1\}$
Chance Constraint Indicator	$z_{j,\omega} \in \{0, 1\} \forall j, \omega \in \mathbf{R}, \Omega$

TABLE V: Complete Formulation of the BCMIP-CC

A. Sensitivity analysis of Deterministic Model

Prior to formulating the BCMIP-CC we evaluated the assumptions of the deterministic BCMIP. To conduct this evaluation we established a *baseline* of current QOL TTPs decisions specifying how the US Army currently designs base camps to evaluate the performance of the BCMIP. To build this QOL baseline we referenced several regional command Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) documents and the current Base Camp US Army Field Manual (FM 3-37.20). [13], [12], [6] For an initial performance evaluation, we optimized the BCMIP and compared the resulting recommended QOL decisions to the QOL score achieved by current QOL TTPs decisions (measured by the objective function developed by the Natick Labs SLB-STO-D). Table I provides this comparison of the optimized QOL decisions determined by the BCMIP (the $\arg \max$ of the BCMIP) and current QOL TTPs, including QOL scores for performance evaluation.

With the baseline QOL TTPs decisions established, we performed numerical sensitivity analysis on the BCMIP to evaluate the assumptions associated the parameters of the model. Numerical sensitivity analysis was performed by perturbing each parameter individually by $\pm 1\%$ and iteratively resolving the BCMIP. Each iteration of optimized solutions were then compared to the initial results of the BCMIP and the baseline QOL TTPs decisions. We first evaluated the sensitivity of the objective function coefficients parameters q_i and marginal use coefficients $u_{i,j}$. We found that the model was insensitive to changes in both these parameters; the details of this analysis can be found in Kuiper. [17]

Next, we evaluated the sensitivity of the BCMIP to resource availability, $b_{\omega,j}$ where $\omega = \{\text{Scenario } 1\} \forall \omega \in \Omega$ for the BCMIP, by iteratively decreasing *all* resources by 1% and resolving the BCMIP with each iteration. Once again we compared each iteration to previous optimized solutions and the baseline. We found that fuel, water, waste water, and solid waste could all be reduced by 29% uniformly while maintaining an equivalent QOL when compared to the score achieved by the baseline. In Figure 1 we provide the results of this analysis.

Fig. 1: Resource Availability Sensitivity Analysis

The results of the resource availability sensitivity analysis confirmed the utility of employing the BCMIP to determine QOL decisions when designing base camps. This analysis also indicated that base camp QOL is sensitive to the resource availability parameter, $b_{\omega,j}$. After investigating the sensitivity of the BCMIP for each resource $j \in \mathbf{R}$ we determined that base camp QOL and soldier mission effectiveness is most impacted by fuel and water availability levels. Figures 2 and 3 provide QOL scores achieved by the BCMIP as fuel and water resource availability levels are reduced. Each iteration of perturbation that results in a QOL score change indicates that the recommended QOL decisions have changed. We've labeled each of these decision points with an integer for reference.

Fig. 2: Fuel Resource Availability Sensitivity Analysis

Fig. 3: Water Resource Availability Sensitivity Analysis

These results align with previous research in the design and sustainment of US Army base camps in contingency operations where the supply of fuel and water acutely impacted soldier QOL and in turn mission effectiveness. [3], [20] This sensitivity analysis of resource availability, coupled with previous research concerning the uncertainty associated with contingency operations, motivated the development of the BCMIP-CC.

B. Analysis of Chance Constraint with Varying Parameters

US Army decision makers must address two fundamental concerns when designing a base camp: 1) how to deal with the uncertainty associated with missing the resupply of resources, often dictated by terrain restrictions, and 2) the level of risk

they are willing to accept when considering the event that the camp does not receive planned resource resupply. The BCMIP-CC provides decision makers with the optimization power of the BCMIP along with two critical tuning parameters. The resource resupply uncertainty value d allows decision makers to adjust the resource availability uncertainty associated with a camp and is an exogenous variable relative to the decision maker. The risk tolerance parameter ϵ adjusts the buffer (additional resource supply beyond daily demand) of resources kept on a base camp, serving as an endogenous variable for the decision maker. Choosing parameters based upon the mission and surrounding terrain of a base camp and then optimizing the BCMIP-CC allows decision makers to guard against the event of reduced resources when designing camps.

The uncertainty associated with the resupply of a base camp as specified in Equation 2 is quantified by the parameter d . This parameter represents the "success" parameter of Bernoulli trial, where "success" is the successful resupply of a limited resource daily to the base camp and "failure" is the missed resupply of a limited resource daily. The decision maker may adjust d smaller (closer to 0) as the terrain surrounding a camp becomes more difficult to travel through to deliver resources. Terrain that is difficult to travel through, or *restricted terrain*, naturally causes resource resupply to become more uncertain leading to a decreased d value. As expected, decreasing the parameter d closer to 0 will decrease the QOL score of a base camp because missing the resupply of a resource becomes more probable, reducing the level of available resources across scenarios $\omega \in \Omega$.

The parameter ϵ is a measure of a camp's guard against uncertainty quantifying a decision maker's risk tolerance for a base camp. This parameter ensures that a camp maintains a resource buffer amount, which is increased for a low risk tolerance camp, and decreased for a high risk tolerance camp. A buffer is a reserve of limited resources, consumed when a resupply is missed. Risk tolerance for a decision maker when designing a base camp is dictated by the mission, for example a complex camp with mission essential aircraft providing international transportation would have much lower risk tolerance than a small simple camp of rifleman.

If all other parameters are kept constant, lowering the risk tolerance for a base camp will result in a reduced QOL score. This is a result of an increased resource buffer, which reduces the amount of resources available to provide QOL services on the camp. A larger buffer provides a stock of resources available to maintain QOL services in the event of missed resource resupply. The BCMIP-CC allows decision makers to quantify the risk they are accepting when designing a camp by sacrificing QOL in order to guard against uncertainty. When a decision maker lowers the risk tolerance of a base camp design, the BCMIP-CC increases the buffer of resources available on the camp to guard against missed resource resupply.

In Table VI we provide the QOL decisions for the optimized BCMIP-CC for two examples of base camps.

Decision	Large Complex Base Camp $\epsilon_j = .05, d = .9$	Small Simple Base Camp $\epsilon_j = .25, d = .5$
Shower	Hot 5 minute	None
Laundry Bags	None	None
Latrines	Chemical Toilets	Chemical Toilets
Breakfast	UGR-A	UGR-A
Lunch	UGR-A	UGR-A
Dinner	UGR-A	UGR-A
Refrigerated Beverages	Not Available	Available
Ice Available	Available	Not Available
Enhanced Food	Available	Available
Gym	Cardio	Cardio and Weight
MWR	Basic	Improved
Mail Facility	Not Available	Available
HVAC	High	None
Score	13.946	12.013

TABLE VI: Comparison of Chance Constraint Analysis

The camps described in Table VI have distinctly different mission sets and resource supply uncertainty. The **Large Complex Base Camp** models a camp where resource availability occurs with little interruption, $d = .9$, and a low tolerance for risk, $\epsilon = .05$. The low tolerance for risk models a complex camp with essential assets or where soldiers rest and reset equipment. Additionally, a missed resupply on larger more complex camps could prove catastrophic given the construction of more complex QOL services, further necessitating a low risk parameter.

The second camp models a **Small Simple Base Camp**, with a much higher likelihood of missed resource resupply and a higher risk tolerance. This parameterization accurately models a forward camp with basic QOL services, where basic services are easily adjusted in the event of a missed resupply when compared to larger complex camps.

IV. CONCLUSION

The QOL decisions employed on base camps during Operation Endure and Iraqi Freedom consumed unsustainable amounts of resources. [3], [18] While consuming large amounts of resources these camps delivered relatively little return in QOL as shown by our analysis of current US Army QOL TTPs. Subsequently, current base camp design and QOL decisions are challenged by the results of the BCMIP-CC. While the results of the deterministic BCMIP demonstrated improvement over current practices, our follow-on sensitivity analysis showed that our initial recommended QOL decisions were sensitive to changes in fuel and water, leading to our recommendation that base camp design account for the possibility of lower fuel and water supply. The BCMIP-CC addressed this uncertainty and we provide two examples of optimized QOL decisions, with uncertainty and risk parameters d and ϵ in Table VI.

The BCMIP-CC is the most important contribution of this investigation; employing a distribution of resource availability is critical to providing effective and efficient QOL decisions

when designing base camps. When compared to relying upon individual anecdotal experience, the BCMIP-CC is a significantly more effective method for establishing base camp design doctrine. The BCMIP-CC parameterizes the uncertainty and risk associated with the QOL design decisions of a base camp, allowing decision makers to deliberately construct efficient camps, while maintaining QOL.

V. FUTURE WORK

A priority of our future work is to explore the impact of changes to the parameters ϵ and d on the results of the BCMIP-CC. Furthermore, we would like to investigate how to estimate numerical values for ϵ and d specific to mission sets and terrain restrictions associated with actual base camps. We would like to determine the correlation between measurable mission effectiveness of soldiers and the QOL score determined by the BCMIP-CC. This would return the quantitative QOL score back to a qualitative metric with practical meaning to US Army decision makers.

Leveraging the final formulation and results of the BCMIP-CC, we believe the US Army can define doctrinal standards for QOL decisions. US Army decision makers should review this investigation, with previous research, to develop doctrinal base camp design standards with regard to QOL. Establishing well defined doctrine employing the methodology developed by this investigation, will improve soldier QOL, mission effectiveness, and reduce the resources required to execute global contingency operations.

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